

Removal of lead(II) ions using synthetic nano iron oxide and commercial activated carbon

G. Kanthimathi*^a, P. Thillai Arasu^a, P. Kotteeswaran^b and M. Kottaisamy^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kalasalingam University, Krishnankoil-626 126, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : kanthi_somu@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Ramco Institute of Technology, Rajapalayam-626 127, Tamilnadu, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Thiagarajar College of Engineering, Madurai-625 115, Tamilnadu, India

Abstract : The adsorbent nano iron oxide (SNIO) was synthesized and essential characteristics were ascertained using FT-IR, SEM and EDAX techniques. Commercially Available Carbon (CAC) was activated further by acid treatment to enhance its adsorption capacity. Adsorption experiments were carried out by using batch method to compare the sorption behaviour of SNIO and CAC for the removal of Pb^{II} ions. The study was conducted on the basis of parameters such as a function of initial concentration of the adsorbate, adsorbent dosage, contact time and pH. Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm models have been tested.

Keywords : SNIO, CAC, adsorption.

Introduction

Lead poisoning leads to haematological damage, gastrointestinal and hematological disturbances, weakening of the central nervous system¹. The tolerance level of Pb^{II} ions for adults suggested by WHO is 7 mg kg⁻¹ of adult body weight per day. But, its presence in most of the industrial and mining effluents, soil of industrial area, water and sewage system is beyond the tolerance limit. Activated carbon is a well known industrial adsorbent and has been studied for the removal of heavy metals from industrial wastes¹ and it is also being widely used in the treatment of potable water. The magnetic nano particles² are potentially useful for the adsorption of pol-

luted ions during waste water treatment, because the nano particles have large surface area, super paramagnetic properties that make them excellent candidates for contaminant removal from polluted water.

Experimental

Preparation of nano Fe₃O₄ :

Synthetic nano iron oxide (SNIO) was synthesized by acid-base hydrolysis of ferrous and ferric chloride. All the chemicals were of reagent grade (SD Fine) and were used without further purification. The flow diagram for the preparation of the nano iron oxide is given below.

Results and discussion

Infra-red spectroscopy (IR) :

FT-IR spectrum for synthesized nano Fe_3O_4 were measured by using a Shimadzu 8400S Japan FT-IR spectrophotometer following KBr pellet technique in the range of wave number $4000\text{--}410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and as given in Fig. 1. The broad band around 3425 cm^{-1} is attributed to the hydroxyl group of water molecules adsorbed by the adsorbents. The bands around 1635 cm^{-1} are due to C=C stretching vibrations³. The bands around 1580 cm^{-1} may be due to C-H stretching vibrations. The band at 573 cm^{-1} and 570 cm^{-1} are due to the stretching frequency of Fe-O in nano Fe_3O_4 respectively. They are characteristically pronounced for all spinel structures and for ferrite in particular.

Fig. 1. Infra-red spectrum of synthetic nano Fe_3O_4 .

SEM observation for the nano adsorbent Fe_3O_4 :

Fig. 2a shows the high resolution scanning electron microscope (HRSEM) image of Fe_3O_4 particles with size distribution varying from 18 nm to 22 nm after treating with lead solution, the particles show an increased agglomeration and surface of the particles appears to be smooth in Fig. 2a. An X-ray energy dispersion analysis (EDAX) of Fe_3O_4 after adsorption of lead solution is shown in Fig. 2b. From the EDAX spectrum, it is observed that Fe and O are the major components along with the presence of Pb adsorbed by it.

Effect of initial concentration :

In order to study the effect of initial concentration, the adsorption experiments were carried out at different initial concentrations (60–125 ppm for CAC, 250–600 ppm for SNIO) of the Pb^{II} ions, keeping the dose rate of SNIO (1.07 g/L) and CAC (10 g/L), contact time (60 min for both SNIO and CAC) and pH (6–6.5 for SNIO, 6.5–7 for

Fig. 2a. SEM micrograph for lead adsorbed in nano Fe_3O_4 .

Fig. 2b. EDAX for nano Fe_3O_4 after adsorption of Pb^{II} ions.

CAC) for each system to be constant. The variation in the percentage removal of the Pb^{II} ions with their concentrations are diagrammatically represented in Fig. 3. In both cases of adsorbents it was observed that the percentage of removal of Pb^{II} ions is low at higher concentration and gradually increases as the concentration of

Fig. 3. Effect of concentration on the adsorption of Pb^{II} ions by CAC and SNIO.

Pb^{II} ions decreases. This is due to the fact that after the formation of mono-ionic layer at lower concentration over the adsorbent surface, further formation of the layer is highly hindered at higher concentration due to the interaction between Pb^{II} ions present on the surface and in the solution. In addition to that, at low concentration of the Pb^{II} ions, the ratio of the initial number of moles of the Pb^{II} ions to the available surface area of the adsorbent is large and subsequently, the fraction of the adsorption becomes independent of the initial concentration of the metal ion. But at a higher concentration, the adsorption sites available for the adsorption become lesser, and hence, the percentage removal of the metal ions at a higher concentration decreases⁴. The optimum concentration of the Pb^{II} ions is found to be 300 ppm by adsorption on SNIO with the resulting percentage removal of 99.7%. For CAC the optimum concentration of the Pb^{II} ions is found to be 65 ppm with the resulting percentage removal of 89.07%.

Effect of dose rate on the removal of Pb^{II} ions :

The adsorption efficiency of SNIO and CAC for the removal of Pb^{II} ions was studied with different dose of SNIO (0.25–2.57 g/L) and CAC (2.5–20.0 g/L) at the optimum concentration of 300 ppm (SNIO) and 65 ppm (CAC) with fixed contact time of 60 min and pH 6–6.5 for SNIO and pH 6.5–7 for CAC and temperature 28 ± 1 °C. The results are pictorially represented in Fig. 4. It is noted that the percentage removal of the Pb^{II} ions increases as the adsorbent concentration increases owing to

Fig. 4. Effect of dose rate on the adsorption Pb^{II} ions by adsorption on SNIO and CAC.

the enhanced total surface area of the adsorbent. The removal of the Pb^{II} ions increases slightly with increase in the dose of SNIO and CAC. This means that the toxic ions can be removed effectively from the contaminated

water with the proper amount of the adsorbent, which would possess more adsorption sites available for the metal ion uptake from the solution. The SNIO shows higher adsorption capacity (99.7%) with the optimum dose of 1.07 g/L which is nearly ten times less than CAC (89.07% at 10.0 g/L), because the nano particles possess more number of micropores and mesopores and higher total surface energy than macroparticles which are more prone to adsorb the Pb^{II} ions on to the surface of the adsorbent in order to decrease the total free energy⁴.

Effect of contacting time for the removal of Pb^{II} ions :

In order to study the effect of the contact time on the removal of the Pb^{II} ions, the adsorption experiments were carried out at different contact times at optimum concentrations of the metal ions with the respective dose of SNIO and CAC. The relevant experimental data are presented in Fig. 5. The values of percentage removal of Pb^{II} ions and amount adsorbed was exponential at the beginning of the contact time and then became stagnated as contact

Fig. 5. Effect of contact time on the adsorption of Pb^{II} ions by CAC and SNIO.

time increased. The equilibrium time for the maximum removal of the Pb^{II} ions is found to be 60 min for SNIO with the effective adsorption of 99.7%, for CAC also, 60 min with the effective adsorption of 89.07%.

Effect of pH of the solution :

The adsorption potential of SNIO and CAC is measured at various pH values, keeping the system at the optimum conditions of the initial concentration of the Pb^{II} ions, adsorbent dose and contact time. The relevant experimental data are graphically represented in Fig. 6. The removal of the Pb^{II} ions through adsorption by SNIO and CAC is effective in slightly acidic medium and the optimum pH range observed for SNIO is 6.5 and CAC

Fig. 6. Effect of pH on the adsorption of Pb^{II} ions by adsorption on CAC and SNIO.

7.2. The percentage removal of metal ions is low at low pH and increases with the increase in pH. At optimum pH (6.5 for SNIO, 7.2 for CAC) the concentration of the H⁺ ions is lowered and consequently, the adsorption of the Pb^{II} ions increases. At higher pH than the optimum, the OH⁻ ion concentration is increased and preferentially adsorbed on the adsorbent and the surface of the adsorbent becomes negatively charged⁴. Moreover at higher pH, the Pb^{II} ions form various complex anions, hydroxide complexes, etc. which are retarded by the negatively charged surface of the adsorbent. At optimum pH (pH 6.5) SNIO shows higher adsorption capacity of 99.7% whereas the CAC (pH 7.2) shows only 89.07%.

Adsorption isotherm :

When the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm are plotted, linear plots are observed and shown in Figs. 7a and 7b. The linearity indicates the applicability of both the isotherms for the Pb^{II} ions on SNIO and CAC. Various useful parameters like adsorption capacities (Q_0) of SNIO and CAC, energy of adsorption (B), separation factor (R) and correlation co-efficient (r^2) obtained from various models are presented in Table 1. Adsorption capacity is found to be high for SNIO ($Q_0 = 500 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$) than CAC ($Q_0 = 11.11 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$), and the energy of the adsorption is found to be less for SNIO ($B = 0.14 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$) than CAC

Fig. 7a. Freundlich isotherm.

Fig. 7b. Langmuir isotherm.

Table 1. Freundlich and Langmuir constants derived from the simultaneous removal of Pb^{II} ions by using CAC and SNIO

Adsorbent	Freundlich constant			Langmuir constant			
	K	$1/n$	r^2	Q_0 (mg g^{-1})	B (L mg^{-1})	R	r^2
CAC	2.8	0.3	0.99	11.11	0.15	0.09	0.99
SNIO	83.17	0.3	0.99	500	0.14	0.02	0.99

($B = 0.15 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$). The higher adsorption capacity and low energy of adsorption for SNIO may be due to the larger surface area and the highly active surface sites present in SNIO than CAC. The separation factor R obtained for the removal of Pb^{II} ions by SNIO (0.02) and the CAC (0.09) are found to be between 0 and 1 indicating the feasibility of the adsorption. The adsorption intensity $1/n$ values for SNIO and CAC are > 0.05 indicating a strong bond formation between the adsorbate and the adsorbent during the adsorption.

Conclusions

In the present study, the efficiency of SNIO towards the removal of the Pb^{II} ions was examined and compared with that of CAC. The optimum conditions of the various factors for the maximum removal of the Pb^{II} ions arrived at from the studies are given in Table 2. The

Table 2. The optimum conditions of the various factors for the maximum removal of the Pb^{II} ions arrived at from the studies

Parameter	SNIO	CAC
Optimum concentration of the Pb ^{II} ion (ppm)	300	65
Optimum dose rate (g/L)	1.07	10
Optimum contact time (min)	60	60
Optimum pH	6–6.5	6.5–7
Percentage removal (%)	99.7	89.07
Adsorption capacity (mg/g)	500	11.11
Energy of adsorption (L/mg)	0.14	0.15
Amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent (q_e) (mg g^{-1})	279.76	5.79

higher adsorption capacity, higher rate constant of adsorption and lower energy of the adsorption of the SNIO compared to the CAC attributed to the large surface area and higher active surface sites of the SNIO. Hence, SNIO may be considered to be a superior alternative adsorbent for the removal of the Pb^{II} ions than CAC, because SNIO is less expensive, eco-friendly, time saving and the adsorbed metal ions can be easily desorbed by increasing the temperature and hence it can be used repeatedly.

References

1. C. P. Huang and M. H. Wu, *J. Water Pol. Cont. Fed.*, 1975, **47**, 2437.
2. W. X. Zhang, *Journal of Nanoparticle Research*, 2003, **5**, 323.
3. Y. F. Shen, J. Tang, Z. H. Nie, Y. D. Wang, Y. Ren and L. Zuo, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2009, **68**, 312.
4. D. Prodan, C. Chanéac, E. Tronc, J. P. Jolivet, R. Cherkaour, A. Ezzir, M. Noguès and J. L. Dormann, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.*, 1999, **203**, 63.